

**NOTES ON NAZAR ESHONQUL'S NOVEL
"GO'RO'G'LI"****Akhmadjanova Zulfiya Ilyos kizi****Teacher at the Bekobod Campus of Tashkent****University of Economics and Pedagogy****akhmadjanovazulfiya@gmail.com,****+998901261906****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20742129>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 13th June 2026Accepted: 15th June 2026Online: 17th June 2026**KEYWORDS***literature, independence, prose,
novel, modernism, absurdism,
epigraph, oral folk literature***ABSTRACT**

The literature of the Independence period occupies a special place in the history of Uzbek literature. This period is distinguished by its unique characteristics, distinctive style and content, as well as its modernist features. This article analyzes these specific qualities and distinctive aspects through the example of the novel "Go'ro'g'li" by Nazar Eshonqul. Through the inner suffering of a person who is unable to prove his own existence, the novel reveals the oppressive atmosphere characteristic of the era.

Introduction:

As we become acquainted with examples of Uzbek literature of the Independence period, we directly witness that the works created during this era emerged in an entirely different and innovative form. In the literature of this period, the exploration of the human psyche, the revelation of its unique features, and its analysis came to the forefront, surpassing the depiction of external reality. At first glance, such unconventionality gave rise to incomprehension, absurdity, and abstraction. A new spirit emerged in the literature of this period; literary works began to be perceived in a new way, and the very process of perception itself became a significant phenomenon. Literary scholars explained this reality through the concept of "modernism." In this regard, it is appropriate to cite Nazar Eshonqul's definition of modernism: "Modernizm – yangilik degani, yangicha tasavvur, yangicha qabul qilish, degani. Uning boshqa ma'nosi yo'q. Adabiyotni esa olabo'ji bilan qo'rqitib bo'lmaydi. U hassalardan qo'rqib emas, ong va did ehtiyoji bo'lib yangilanaveradi, o'zgaraveradi". [1] These innovations found vivid expression in prose, poetry, and drama alike. During the Independence period, Uzbek prose was liberated from the pressure and constraints of socialist realism, embarked upon a new path of artistic representation of life, and achieved notable successes in this sphere. Our prose writers began not only to depict distant and recent historical realities in a new way but also to create diverse works in various genres devoted directly to the Independence period itself. As a result, a noticeable tendency emerged in our literature to portray the realities of the Independence era and transform the heroes of the new age into literary characters. As an echo of this renewal, novels such as Nazar Eshonqul's "Go'ro'g'li yoxud hayot suvi", To'xtamurod Rustamov's "Kapalaklar o'yini", Luqmon Bo'rixon's "Jaziramadagi odamlar" became subjects of extensive debates and discussions among literary enthusiasts. Despite differences in artistic style, plot structure, psychological transformations

of characters, artistic depiction, and poetic language, these three novels are connected by common threads that invite deeper reflection.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

As Nazar Eshonqul himself emphasizes, the novel “Go‘ro‘g‘li yoxud hayot suvi” appears before the reader as a work permeated by “Devorlarini zax bosgan, qulash arafasiga kelib qolgan, insonning botiniy quvvatini so‘rish evaziga yashagan tuzumning badbo‘y hidlari anqib turgan”. The epigraph, which resonates like a preface to the novel, serves as a clear mirror reflecting the entire essence of the work: “... hayot suvin izlab o‘tdi Gilgamish”. [2] This excerpt from the Epic of Gilgamesh directly alludes to the protagonist N. and to his actions throughout the narrative. While Gilgamesh sought life, existence, and the water of immortality, N. spends his life searching for a way to convince others of the life that already exists within him. Unfortunately, the remedy he seeks remains trapped within the cold grip of a totalitarian system. Even the title of the work astonishes the reader through its complete departure from established conventions: Go‘ro‘g‘li. Why Go‘ro‘g‘li? As we delve deeper into the novel, the answer gradually becomes apparent. Although N.’s fate did not decree that he be born in a grave like the legendary Go‘ro‘g‘li, the grave pursues him throughout his life, constantly inviting him into its cold embrace.

Perhaps we are judging only from the inner perspective when we claim that N. was not born in a grave. If we also consider the external aspect, perhaps he was born in a grave from the very beginning. There exists an undeniable truth of life: “Man was created from earth and will inevitably return to earth.” Perhaps N. too was born in a grave and one day returned to it. If we remember that the novel presents a picture of the repulsive face of the Soviet system, this assumption gains further confirmation. Indeed, N. was born into a period even more painful than a grave — the era known as the totalitarian regime — and it is natural that this system continuously threatened his very existence. In most great literary works, the opening and closing sentences carry decisive significance. They encapsulate the entire content of the work and explain its role as a complete artistic reality. The novel begins with the sentence: “N. ni yangi lavozimga tavsiya qilishdi” [2] It concludes with the following passage:

“U yaqinlashib qolgan poyezdga qarab qadam tashladi va so‘nggi bor vokzalga, bir-birini turtib, surtib borayotgan olomonga ko‘z tashladi – u yerda uni go‘rkov – sud ijrochisi kuzatib turar, go‘yo u sud hukmining qanday ijro etilishini ko‘rgani kelganday edi; N. oxirgi daqiqada go‘rkovning ko‘zini eslashga tirishdi; biroq eslolmadi va shu holicha, xuddi Iskandar kabi men ham qo‘limda hech narsa olib ketayotganim yo‘q degandek o‘zini qora bo‘shliq ichiga otdi” [2]

The novel thus begins with an illusion of happiness, success, and prosperity, yet ends with bitter truth, immense misfortune, endless suffering, painful failure, and the destruction of a man exhausted by trying to prove that he is alive. Having submitted to the verdict imposed upon him by the servants of the Soviet regime, he ultimately perishes and truly dies. There is wisdom in the saying that the distance between good and evil, happiness and unhappiness, fulfillment and illusion is only a single step. The same is true in this novel. It begins with happiness — even if false — and ends with genuine misery. Even the contrast between the brevity of the opening sentence and the extraordinary length of the closing sentence seems meaningful. Perhaps the author wished to suggest that happiness is brief, arriving swiftly and

ending just as quickly, whereas unhappiness comes with prolonged suffering and remains constantly present.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Certain words and references within the novel demonstrate the author's skillful use of folklore and oral tradition. The epigraph taken from the Epic of Gilgamesh, the title of the novel, the reference to Alexander at the end, and the name of the scholar Shomon all support this view. From beginning to end, the work is dominated by abstraction and a labyrinth-like atmosphere. This sense of abstraction is reinforced by the fact that the names of characters and political institutions are not revealed in full but represented only by initials. Some characters even appear under different names and identities at different points in the narrative. For example, the woman to whom N. proposes marriage is initially named Havo, but later appears as Guli. Correspondingly, the sentences revealing the protagonist's inner world also undergo changes. Such techniques create a certain degree of confusion for the reader.

CONCLUSIONS:

In conclusion, it can be stated that the literature of the Independence period entered the literary arena with a completely new and previously unseen appearance. Both poetry and prose produced works imbued with a distinctly modernist spirit. Such transformations are clearly evident in almost all of Nazar Eshonqul's works, particularly in the novel "Go'ro'g'li yoxud hayot suvi".

As we read these works, we can clearly perceive the profound influence of renowned Western modernist writers, especially Franz Kafka. This influence constitutes one of the most important characteristics of Uzbek prose during the Independence period.

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